

A STUDY OF OCCUPATIONAL STRESS TOWARDS HIGHER SECONDARY TEACHERS OF MATHEMATICS

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Abstract:

Stress occurs when workers perceive an imbalance between their capability and resources to meet these demands. It is that which derives from conditions in the workplace. Occupational Stress, in particular, is the inability to cope with the pressures of a job. It is a mental and physical condition that affects an individual's productivity, effectiveness, personal health and quality of work. So, the main aim of this study is to investigate the occupational stress towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics. This study aims to identify occupational stress towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics. The sample of 280 teachers of mathematics in higher secondary schools was selected from government with government aided and private located in Vellore district. Data analysis was done using inferential statistics with the aid of 22 Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The findings of the study revealed that there is no significant difference in occupational stress towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics towards gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction, Teaching Experience (Years) and marital status of higher secondary school teachers.

Key Words: Occupational Stress, Mathematics Teachers, Distribution

Introduction:

It is the teacher who matters the most as far as the quality of education is concerned. A well-equipped teacher is supreme in education and is the pivot in the system of education. Developing a quality and effective understandings among the teachers is possible when we make a stress free environment, which has been studied widely by different researchers from time to time. In our lives stress is a common feature. A phrase that stress collapses everything has a prominent place in the minds of millions, and everyone thinks that it is a silent killer in the modern age.

An occupational stress is any force that pushes a psychological or physical factor behind its range of stability, producing a strain within the individuals. Knowledge that stress is likely to occur constitutes a threat to the individual. A threat can cause a strain because of what it signifies to the person. As occupational stress begins to take toll on the body and mind, a variety of symptoms can result.

Working in organisations not only provides individuals with life sustaining income but also exerts its own pressures on them. This can ultimately have negative consequences both for achieving the goals of the organisation and meeting the needs of the individuals working in them. Thus, the work environment is a source of social and psychological stress, which has harmful effects on the well-being of the employees. Stress in general and occupational stress in particular is universal and frequently disabling human phenomenon. Stress arising at work has detrimental effect on the behaviour of people, which ultimately results in personal and organisational inefficiency. Occupational stress can be described as a condition where occupation related factors interact with the worker to change (disrupt/ enhance) his or her psychological or physiological condition, so that the person's mind and/or body is forced to deviate from its normal way of functioning. T.A. Beehr, and J.E. Newman (1978).

Statement of the Problem:

The progress of a nation is limited to its productive capacity, which in turn depends upon the calibre of its occupational stress towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics. The education system in general and the higher secondary teachers system in particular are instruments to develop the human capital as economic assets for wealth generation and also as social assets for improving the quality of the life of the people. The problem selected for the study of occupational stress towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics.

Objectives of the Study:

To find out, if there is any significant difference in occupational stress towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics belonging to following sub samples

- Gender : Male/ Female
- Locality of School : Rural / Urban
- Type of Management : Government / Govt Aided / Private
- Medium of Instruction : Tamil / English / Both
- Teaching Experience (Years) : Below 10/ 11 -20/ Above 21
- Marital Status : Married / Unmarried

Hypotheses of the Study:

There is no significant difference in occupational stress towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics belonging to following sub samples

- Gender : Male/ Female
- Locality of School : Rural / Urban
- Type of Management : Government / Govt Aided / Private
- Medium of Instruction : Tamil / English / Both
- Teaching Experience (Years) : Below 10/ 11 -20/ Above 21
- Marital Status : Married / Unmarried

Sample of the Study:

The investigator had used for selecting the sample. The investigator randomly selected the teachers from higher secondary teachers of mathematics. The selection was done on the basis of the gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction, teaching experience in years and marital status. From these schools 280 higher school teachers were randomly selected on the basis of the criteria.

Tool Used for the Present Study:

Occupational Stress by Dr. A. K. Srivastava and Singh

Description of the tool Occupational Stress:

The specially prepared scale developed by Dr. A. K. Srivastava and Singh was selected to know the occupational stress scale of the employee. It measures the occupational stress in a scientific manner. In these scale 46 different questions was to measure higher secondary school teachers employee. The respondent is required to answer the question in following options: Absolutely True, almost true, partially true, almost false and absolutely false .i.e 5 marks for absolutely false and 1 mark for absolutely true. Thus a respondent can obtain minimum 46 (46*1) score and maximum 230 (46*5) score. The interpretation of the scale was done on the basis of marks obtained; if the marks were high the level of occupational stress was high while lower marks represent low stress level.

Differential Analysis - Occupational Stress:

Table 1: Mean, S.D. and “t” Values of Occupational Stress of Higher Secondary Teachers of Mathematics towards Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	“t” Value	Significant at 0.05 level
Male	158	164.19	11.51	0.717	NS
Female	122	163.23	10.51		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between male and female occupational stress score towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics the investigator calculated ‘t’ value. It is given in the Table No 1, it is found to be 0.717, which is not significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that male and female higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.

Table 2: Mean, S.D. and “t” Values of Occupational Stress of Higher Secondary Teachers of Mathematics towards Locality of School

Locality of School	N	Mean	SD	“t” Value	Significant at 0.05 level
Rural	88	163.06	10.62	0.726	NS
Urban	192	164.10	11.29		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between rural and urban occupational stress score towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics the investigator calculated ‘t’ value. It is given in the Table No 2, it is found to be 0.726, which is not significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that rural and urban higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.

Table 3: “F” Values of Occupational Stress of Higher Secondary Teachers of Mathematics towards Type of Management

Group	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	‘F’ Value	LS
Between Groups	848.475	2	424.238	3.517	NS
Within Groups	33415.796	277	120.635		
Total	34264.271	279			

In order to find out the significant mean difference among government, government aided and private type of management of occupational stress score towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics the investigator calculated 'F' value. It is given in the Table No- 3 it is found to be 3.517, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that government, govt aided and private type of management of higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.

Table 4: "F" Values of Occupational Stress of Higher Secondary Teachers of Mathematics towards Medium of Instruction

Group	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' value	LS
Between Groups	340.437	2	170.218	1.390	NS
Within Groups	33923.835	277	122.469		
Total	34264.271	279			

In order to find out the significant mean difference among Tamil, English and both of medium of instruction occupational stress score towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics the investigator calculated 'F' value. It is given in the Table No- 4 it is found to be 1.390, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that Tamil, English and both medium of instruction of higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.

Table 5: "F" Values of Occupational Stress of Higher Secondary Teachers of Mathematics towards Teaching Experience

Group	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' Value	LS
Between Groups	928.342	2	464.171	3.857	NS
Within Groups	33335.929	277	120.346		
Total	34264.271	279			

In order to find out the significant mean difference among and below 10, 11-20 and above 21 years of teaching experience of occupational stress score towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics the investigator calculated 'F' value. It is given in the Table No- 5, it is found to be 3.857, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that below 10, 11-20 and above 21 years of teaching experience of higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.

Table 6: Mean, S.D. and "t" Values of Occupational Stress of Higher Secondary Teachers of Mathematics towards Marital Status

Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	"t" Value	Significant at 0.05 level
Married	130	164.25	10.57	0.667	NS
Unmarried	150	163.36	11.52		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between married and unmarried occupational stress score towards higher secondary teachers of mathematics the investigator calculated 't' value. It is given in the Table No 6, it is found to be 0.667, which is not significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that married ad unmarried higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.

Major Findings:

- It is inferred that male and female higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.
- It is inferred that rural and urban higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.
- It is inferred that government, govt aided and private type of management of higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.
- It is inferred that Tamil, English and both medium of instruction of higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.
- It is inferred that below 10, 11-20 and above 21 years of teaching experience of higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.
- It is inferred that married ad unmarried higher secondary teachers of mathematics do not differ significantly in their occupational stress.

Conclusion:

Occupational stress in the workplace is becoming a major concern for all teachers, headmasters and government, owing to the occupational health and safety legislations requiring employers to practice by providing teachers with safe working environments which also cover the psychological well being of their staff. The reduction of occupational stress will induce the teachers to provide efficient and effective service to the society. For the betterment of the educational institutions the occupational stress among the higher secondary school teachers should be reduced. The most important benefit in reducing occupational stress is that it will

promote a pleasurable work environment for all. The study throws light on the fact that occupational stress is quite a personal matter and that the perception of the situation enables one to cope with it effectively, being aware of the causes of occupational stress and monitoring properly.

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